

Automatic identification of structure function of scientific full text in Journal of Informetric Based on Deep Learning

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Introduction

The increasing number of open-access full-text scientific documents promotes the transformation from metadata-based to content-based research which is more detailed and semantic. Along with the benefits of full text data, the confused internal structure function introduces great difficulties to data organization and analysis (Lu et al., 2018). In citation analysis, research on the structure of scientific articles helps to determine the citation location better. In recent years, deep learning technology has been widely used in automatic identification of the structure function of scientific articles (Ma et al., 2022). In some citation analysis research, the structural function of scientific papers is used as the distinguishing node to explore the citation position (Hu et al., 2013).

This research explores how models such as TextCNN, TextLSTM, BERT and SciBERT work in identification of the structure function of scientific articles in *Journal of Informetrics (JOI)*.

Data Source and Methods

Data source

In this research, data were from 1098 articles in *Journal of Informetrics (JOI)* during 2007- 2020. These articles can be searched by springer platform (<https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/journal-of-informetrics>). The academic full-text data of *JOI* from 2013 to 2020 is used as the training data set and validation data set of the model, and the data from 2007 to 2012 is used as the testing data set.

Methods

A corpus of 1,098 full texts manually annotated with specified structure function categories (Introduction-Literature review-Methods-Results-Conclusions, ILMRC) were constructed. This research explored the identification of structure function in the data set by using TextCNN, TextLSTM, BERT and SciBERT.

Results

TextCNN, TextLSTM, BERT and SciBERT models have been trained. The values of the hyperparameters are as listed below: the batch_size of TextCNN and TextLSTM is 256, the learning_rate of TextCNN is 1e-4, and that of TextLSTM is 1e-3. BERT and SciBERT have the same hyperparameters, and the batch_size is 32, learning_rate is 1e-3. The performance of each model was evaluated by Precision, Recall, F1 values and the Macroaverage.

Table 1. Results of validation data set of four models

Model	BERT			SciBERT		
	precision	recall	f1-score	precision	recall	f1-score
Introduction	87.54%	95.64%	91.41%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%
Literature review	97.45%	93.19%	95.27%	99.09%	94.94%	96.97%
Methods	92.15%	92.15%	92.15%	94.44%	97.73%	96.06%
Results	91.62%	93.54%	92.57%	98.79%	99.30%	99.04%
Conclusions	91.56%	85.17%	88.25%	96.86%	97.03%	96.95%
MACRO-Avg	92.06%	91.94%	91.93%	97.84%	97.80%	97.80%
Model	Text LSTM			Text CNN		
	precision	recall	f1-score	precision	recall	f1-score
Introduction	99.82%	98.78%	99.30%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%
Literature review	86.22%	97.21%	91.39%	93.54%	98.60%	96.01%
Methods	98.40%	96.68%	97.54%	98.94%	97.38%	98.15%
Results	95.40%	90.40%	92.83%	97.70%	96.51%	97.10%
Conclusions	94.87%	90.40%	92.58%	99.46%	96.86%	98.14%
MACRO-Avg	94.94%	94.69%	94.73%	97.93%	97.87%	97.88%

The best identification in the Introduction is the SciBERT and TextCNN, with the average F1 value of 100%. In the Literature review, the best identification is the SciBERT, with F1 up to 96.97%. The best Methods r identification is TextCNN, and the average F1 value is 98.15%. In the Results, the best is SciBERT, whose average F1 value reaches 99.04%. TextCNN is the best to identify the Conclusion, and the average F1 value of is 98.14%.

Table 2. Results of testing data set of four models

Model	BERT			SciBERT		
	precision	recall	f1-score	precision	recall	f1-score
Introduction	82.74%	89.37%	85.93%	99.46%	98.49%	98.97%
Literature review	71.07%	92.20%	80.27%	70.77%	94.15%	80.80%
Methods	82.53%	70.90%	76.27%	88.55%	73.89%	80.56%
Results	82.75%	73.98%	78.12%	92.95%	83.78%	88.13%
Conclusions	82.41%	77.86%	80.08%	89.94%	91.97%	90.94%
MACRO-Avg	80.30%	80.86%	80.13%	88.33%	88.46%	87.88%
Model	Text LSTM			Text CNN		
	precision	recall	f1-score	precision	recall	f1-score
Introduction	99.66%	97.69%	98.67%	99.48%	98.41%	98.94%
Literature review	60.63%	95.39%	74.13%	66.29%	97.48%	78.92%
Methods	93.78%	70.24%	80.32%	90.26%	73.38%	80.95%
Results	86.38%	73.12%	79.19%	92.49%	77.91%	84.58%
Conclusions	91.49%	88.39%	89.91%	94.18%	93.08%	93.63%
MACRO-Avg	86.39%	84.96%	84.45%	88.54%	88.05%	87.40%

The overall performance of SciBERT and TextCNN is higher than that of TextLSTM and BERT. The performance of BERT is much lower than the other three models. For the testing data set, the overall performance of SciBERT is the best in terms of structure function identification performance, with the macro average F1 value of 87.88%. The BERT, which does not use random initialization self-vector, has only 80.13% of macro average F1 in this task.

Conclusions

Based on TextCNN, TextLSTM, BERT and SciBERT, according to the data of Journal of Informetrics (JOI), this research realizes the automatic identification of the structure function of scientific articles in the field of library and information science. However, due to the limitation of the amount of training data, there is overfitting of the model, which can be optimized by expanding the training corpus in the future.

From the recognition effect of each structure, the introduction, Literature review and Results part have the best recognition effect of Sci-BERT model, the methods and conclusions part has the best recognition effect of TextCNN model. Judging from the structural recognition ability of the same model, among the recognition results of the four models, the recognition performance of the introduction, conclusions and results part declined in turn, and the worst part was the Literature review part. This may be because this part of the content is similar to other parts, resulting in recognition errors. Generally speaking, Sci-BERT and Text CNN models can better identify the structure function of scientific articles.

Acknowledgments

This study was supported by the National Natural Science Foundation of China (Grant Numbers: 71974094).

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